

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

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Effective management of subordinates and support from company strengths to achieve management goals. Human resource management is one of the first issues that many companies manage, study this science and manage modern technology.

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Human resource management refers to the loading of these resources for the purposes of the organization, the implementation of which involves the development of software and the production of a product. Accordingly, maximizing the knowledge, skills, and competencies of a member of the organization to solve and apply management means “optimizing human resources”. In order to manage employees competently, you need to have a clear understanding of the purpose and role of management. We emphasize three main objectives of human resource management: to contribute short-term business resources to the strategy; maintenance of the strategic plan of business, adjustment of production and implementation; fair and abbreviated, based on the disclosure of the information obtained. Human resource management originated in the United States, then spread to the United Kingdom and other countries. The original concept is a combination of behavioral sciences such as the theory of human capital and the theory of human relations that emerged in the 1960s.

1. Michigan model . 2. Harvard models. 3. Highly effective HRM (Human Resource Management, Human Resource Management). 4. Talent management. As the name suggests, the Michigan model is based on a project at the University of

Michigan in the 1980s and is based on the hypothesis that “human resource management should be done with an emphasis on alignment with business strategies”. The concept includes four key factors: personnel selection; realization of talent; improving human resources; pay for action to support their services. In doing so, it is important to focus on national human resources, but also to manage them with management, such as management strategy, business environment and organizational structure.

Harvard seeks to “achieve organizational and individual goals” through “economic efficiency” through “commitment and challenges” through human resource scrutiny. Shipping from HRM allows you to explore the reasons for high efficiency in a particular company. This model of human resource management consists of three elements: 1. Teamwork. 2. Motivation for something new. 3. Organize and grow. The development of production of each employee in the society leads to the development of new things in the professional and communicative spheres and the improvement of their work. In addition, the company has a “talent management” approach. This applies to the company’s internal system, which prioritizes the talent of its device, so handle qualified care with care. 1.1.1 . _ Talent Management is a management that develops talented people to work in the company's departments. Since employees are the foundation and engine of every company, this is currently the most innovative way to manage these human resources (Human Resources, HR).

HR information is all the information about a company’s human resources, including basic information about each employee, such as: identification information; education; family composition; career growth and salary in both this company and previous jobs; malaka; previous enterprise; collected data loaded to the maximum of the labor potential, degree, level load, using the 360 (720) method. Software and software that may be known by the download process. Against this background, more qualified loading from HR data should consider specific methods and their application, correcting their directions.

Recruiting people who can play an active role in the Organization is a challenge for many companies today. However, if direct data are collected, if necessary, then the analysis of HR data to obtain the best results, to determine the "effective" characteristics of the quality and it will be possible to hit the received data. 'Lady. This will clarify the requirements for the person doing it, and thus the correction of personnel, the acceptance of production. If you use HR to help calves, then it will be possible to learn the help that the employee is showing before retiring. thus, the company needs to take care to find new "reserves" for retirees and to clearly identify the disease obtained by analyzing HR data before it even disappears.

personal, temporary incapacity for work is derived from direct data and tests of employees working at full capacity. To do this, there was a problem with data collection from retirees during the implementation of the methods of use. Three issues can be addressed, in particular, by gathering more accurate information about what the organization is currently up to. Today, it is not possible for HR data (but only by intuition) to unravel the structure of the human self. Downloading from HR data to ensure that this issue is addressed objectively and fairly. This is a means by which many revenue companies implement a replacement production strategy in this way, ensuring that the implementation of each employee's means is maximized, which in turn allows the company to produce production. allows. In other words, HR data is needed to determine the most effective management for a particular employee. If different HR databases are managed centrally in a database, then keep in mind that both development and career plans need to be tailored to each person's qualifications and training. To improve human resource development, it is necessary to increase the amount of specific training, collect and calculate data before and after training to plan the most appropriate training plan for each employee.

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